

**TEST TAKING STRATEGIES USE ON THE
DEVELOPING LISTENING SKILL****Tojiboyeva Madina Ulugbek qizi**<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13641379>

Working with each of the language skills, their formation and integration is the basis of modern methodology. From this point of view, it is very important to explain the importance of listening comprehension skills to the students and work on them. A number of methods can be used to build and develop listening comprehension in modern English, most of which are integrated with other skills. Pre-listening practice activities play a very important role in helping you learn to listen in a foreign language.

They tell teachers how to inform students about what they have learned about the topic and prepare for the word and language structures in the text. In addition to pre-listening exercises, it helps the listeners to clarify what to teach and reduces the anxiety that comes from listening in a foreign language. In addition, pre-listening activities can offer opportunities for class discussion and more interaction between students. Here are some pre-listening activities that can be easily adapted to different levels of English and EAP listening courses. Students can be shown pictures, maps or diagrams to help them identify the topic of the listening text. "Students can write listening questions, exercises, and then listen to them answer the questions." Giving students a listening topic in brainstorming and word networks and from them draw semantic networks on the board with words, focusing on the relationships between themes and sub-themes.

In the teach me method:

Give each student a few words or phrases, ask each other to explain the words and expressions in pairs, they can refer to the dictionary if necessary. Students can listen and mark what they can hear. Chinese noises: put students in two lines, whisper the first word in the line, whisper to the next, and so on, and the next student hears the word or writes the word or its expression on the board. Share a song by entering a sentence or phrase related to the listening topic.

Teach listeners a short song, rhyme, or jazz-related topic. Graphic Organizers: Give students a blank graphic organizer that summarizes the information in the text by line. Students listen and fill in the key words to be heard in the correct places. Students listen to the text and see what ideas are

expressed. In addition, there can be a faster "anonymous" survey, the results of which can be determined at the end of the lesson.

Read the reading exercise first: give the students the first few lines of the intended listening text. You can give them all the transcription and some time to read (just to get the gist of the text). Then work on listening to specific information without a student reading the transcription. This is an effective activity for complex texts with many details. If the conversation of the audience is eavesdropping, then it is possible to arouse the interest of the audience.

Who? If students want to listen to a conversation (or text) with more than one character (and, of course, character identification is not one of the listeners' tasks), consider who the listeners are. What should I do, teacher? Write the instructions in bullet form to listen in the wrong order. Ask students to order them. This activity helps listeners relax to listen because they know exactly what is going to happen next. Note: Discuss the research with students and write brainstorming lines below them to take notes. Then explain the meaning of the transition words you may hear. Depending on the type of text we want to listen to, we should focus on the sub-skills of listening, our students' level and their interests, we match our needs we can select the task before listening to the incoming. We will specifically listen to the lecture and note taking in the next session. That students understand what is expected and assumed during the reading process we can select the task before listening to the incoming. We will specifically listen to the lecture and note taking in the next session.¹

During reading, students can check their understanding of what is expected and expected and what they hear. Students can focus on the following topics: Content. What are the topics and sub-topics? How are topics and subtopics related to each other, speakers use language, and what words do speakers use to introduce new ideas? How do they change this theme? How do they express uncertainty? How does their intonation change throughout the text? In the process of reading, listeners can influence the thoughts of the listeners in the text of the listeners; For example, students can ask themselves: □I Do I agree with what you are saying? Is there another side to what they are saying? Most often, the activity of listeners is focused on the following skills: listening to the audience; Listening to specific information; Listening to the speaker's point of view or opinion. Depending on the listening text we want to use, we should focus on the sub-skills of listening, the level of our students and their interests, we can choose a task that suits our needs. When you plan

¹ Jalolov J.J. *Chet tilli O'qitish metodikasi* -T.: O'qituvchi, 2012

listening tasks, the full recall of all information in the working text, even the we must bear in mind that it is usually difficult and also not expected for people who speak the language. Listening exercises designed for teaching should be successful and build listeners' confidence in their listening skills. Structuring a listening activity around a contextual task. Contextualized listening activities simulate realistic tasks and explain to listeners the type of information expected and what to do before the actual listening. An entry-level task should be to locate locations on a map (one-way) or exchange name and address information (two-way). Intermediate students can follow instructions to set up one object (one-way) or work in pairs to create a story to tell another part of the lesson (two-way). Determine the educational purpose of the activity and the type of response. Each activity should have the goal of improving one or more specific listening skills. Listening exercises can have several goals or outcomes, but care must be taken not to distract from beginning or intermediate listening exercises. Recognizing the listening comprehension goals in each listening situation can help students choose appropriate listening strategies. Identification: Recognizing or distinguishing specific aspects of a message, such as sounds, categories of words, morphological differences. Reference: Identify important messages such as subject, text type, setting. Understanding Main Idea: Identifying higher level ideas. Understanding details is identifying supporting details. Replication: Repeating a message orally or in writing. Check the difficulty level of the listening text. The following factors can help determine the relative ease or difficulty of a listening text for a particular purpose and for a particular group of learners. How is the information organized? Does a different narrative or instruction of the story fit the familiar requirements? Texts that present events in natural chronological order, have informative titles, and present information following a clear organization (main ideas first, details, and examples second) are easier. How familiar are the students with the topic? Be aware that misapplication of knowledge due to cultural differences can create a great difficulty in understanding. Should the text be redundant? Listeners at lower levels of ability can easily process short and simple messages, but students with higher proficiency will benefit from the natural reserve of the language. Does the text cover more than one person and object? Are they distinctly different? A doctor-patient conversation is easier to understand than a conversation between two doctors, even if they are of the opposite gender. In other words, the more differences there are, the easier it is to understand. The text provides clues to help the audience interpret what they hear. Aids such as

maps, diagrams, pictures or images in the videos are useful to make the listening process meaningful and to show the meanings. Use pre-listening activities to prepare students for what they will hear or see.²

Pre-listening activities can be made ready for listening in several ways. During the first listening session, the teacher can explore the topic and evaluate the linguistic content of the text to see if the audience can activate the background knowledge or the students' existing knowledge needed to understand the listening text. Providing opportunities for group or collaborative work, background teaching, or class discussion activities is essential to help students understand the type of text they will be listening to, what role they will play, and the purpose(s) of what they are listening to. Sample listening activities: looking at pictures, maps, charts or graphs, looking at words or grammatical structures, reading what you need, semantic networks (indicating their connection concepts or graphic arrangement of words), creating a listening text, learning activities or directions, conducting guided practice, educational listening activities, listening goals, and student proficiency levels. The listening activity exercises are directly related to the text and the students will be listening to it while they are listening. Keep these points in mind when planning the listening exercises: if students have to complete a written task before or immediately after listening, read it before listening. Students should focus on the listening task. Make sure they understand the instructions for the written task before listening, so they don't just get distracted by what they need to do. At least keep writing while listening. Remember, the main goal is understanding, not production. Having to write in an audition can distract students from this main goal. If a written response is required after the hearing, this task may be more demanding. Organize activities to guide the audience through the text. Combine global activities with listening activities and choosing a main idea, theme, and setting. Questions should be used to focus students' attention on elements of the text that are crucial to overall understanding. Before the audition process begins, students must provide an oral or written response after the audition. Listening to the answers helps students understand the important parts of the message. Use advance to encourage listeners to check their listening comprehension. Do a pre-listening activity and remind the listeners to check whether the passage makes sense in terms of their prior knowledge and what they know about the topics or events. Report immediately where

² D. Adamson, "Inter-language variation in theoretical and pedagogical perspective", London, 2008.

possible. Encourage students to check their answers to see if they are correct or incorrect. Types of sample-listening activities: Listening with information; filling in graphs and tables; follow the route on the map; check items on the list; listen to the speech; to search for specific meanings; performing complementary exercises; distinguish between official and unofficial lists.

Among the four skills that are important in learning any language, listening comprehension is central. In the field of language teaching and learning, speaking and writing a language is usually considered as the primary language use factor. Listening and reading skills come second. One reason for this may be that it is somewhat difficult to master listening skills. But after the spread of IT technology, listening comprehension has become much easier to pass through different materials in language classes. In addition, it should be noted that most of the students' class time began to be devoted to listening. We have come to believe in the importance of listening more often. In the natural order of learning any language, listening began to take the leading place. Everyone became convinced that the mastery of one skill alone would not produce anything. Teachers began to pay more attention to teaching their students not only speaking fluency, but also listening comprehension. Perfect acquisition and use of a new language requires formation of existing knowledge and learning all the necessary information based on language receptive skills, especially listening and reading skills. In this regard, a language learning program has been created for the convenience of learners. According to the structure of this program, it should not contain any input tests, result or output anything. Listening training is very relevant today, because speech communication is impossible without listening. The concept of listening includes the process of perceiving and understanding spoken speech. Listening is definitely an important aspect in learning English. Modern effective methods of teaching listening skills include everything from interactive exercises to multimedia resources. Listening is considered to be the most learnable skill.

In conclusion Because a little more focus on learning is enhanced through simple and fun activities and ultimately leads to better results. In this case, it doesn't matter whether you work with small or large groups of students, as long as you use one of the following methods to develop yourself.

Unique ways to teach students to listen well:

Interpersonal activity Interpersonal activities are one of the most effective ways to develop strong listening skills in students.

We can add the following to this method:

1. Role playing
2. Mock interviews
3. Interpersonal dialogues
4. Storytelling and more In this, students are divided into small groups of two or three, and they are asked questions according to the style.

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